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REPORT TWO (pp 89-92):

Why was the Paper Entitled "Phosphorylation of ARPP19 by Greatwall renders the amplification of MPF independent of PKA in *Xenopus* oocytes" Authored by Dupre, A., Buffin, E., Roustan, C., Nairn, A.C., Jessus, C., and Haccard, O. and published in the Journal of Cell Science [J. Cell. Sci. (2013) Vol. 126, pp 3916-3926.] not Retracted.

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Abstract. In this Investigative Critique of the paper entitled "Phosphorylation of ARPP19 by Greatwall renders the amplification of MPF independent of PKA in *Xenopus* oocytes", authored by Dupre, A., Buffin, E., Roustan, C., Nairn, A.C., Jessus, C., and Haccard, O. and published in the Journal of Cell Science [J. Cell. Sci. (2013) Vol. 126, pp 3916-3926.], it is explained why this paper was not retracted by corrected. It is also shown that problems remain with some of the figures. The authors of the paper are urged to rebut this Investigative Critique of their paper.

In the above paper, the authors purported to show that phosphorylation of the ARPP19 by Greatwall Protein Kinase promoted its binding to and inhibited Protein phosphatase-2A (PP-2A) that contains the B55 δ subunit and that this process that was controlled by cdk1 had an essential role within the cdk1 auto-amplification loop for entry into the meiotic division. The authors of the above paper suggested that "protein phosphatase-2A-B55 δ , Greatwall and ARPP19 are not only required for entry into meiotic division but are also

pivotal effectors with the cdk1 auto-amplification loop responsible with its independence with respect to the PKA-negative control".

While the above paper provides an elegant theory of the control of meiotic division and auto-amplification loop for entry into the first meiotic division, the data presented are very messy and not very convincing. Initially, anonymous writers posted comments in PUBPEER that showed that there were Unscientific Image Manipulation with respect to Figure 4D and Figure S4 of the paper.

As far as Figure 4D is concerned, apparently, the level of background noise and pattern of a Western Immunoblotting Membrane was selectively reduced by Image Manipulation to hide the fact that there were several protein bands that are either artifacts or are reacting with the antibodies that the authors used to identify PP-2A subunits A, B and C. in *Xenopus* oocytes arrested at prophase or in oocytes that were treated with progesterone. The Figure in question was meant to show that ARPP19 formed a complex with PP-2A-B55d when ARPP-19 was first phosphorylated by Greatwall Protein Kinase. What is somewhat strange about Figure 4D is that the authors showed that the three subunits of PP-2A-B55d were detected by their respective antibodies in a single membrane implying that the development of the three PP-2A-B55d subunits with bound primary antibodies were done simultaneously with three primary antibodies, two of which were raised in guinea pigs (A and C antibodies) and one of which was raised in rabbits (anti-B-55d). Under normal circumstances one would have three separate membranes and do the development of the three PP-2A-B55d subunits separately if one wanted to reduce non-specific reactions. The same concern applies for the reactions with secondary antibodies. Were the reactions with secondary antibodies performed simultaneously on one membrane with two different labeled secondary antibodies? Unfortunately, the details of the antibodies reactions were not provided in the Method Section. It is therefore difficult to make any assessment concerning the accuracy and legitimacy of the results presented in Figure 4D. Be that as it may, an Anonymous Scientific Panel at the Universite Pierre et Marie Curie/CNRS determined that there was no Scientific Misconduct involved [1,2] and that there was no need to retract the above

paper. The Journal of Cell Science accepted the recommendation of the Anonymous Investigative Panel at the Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and a new Figure 4D was provided. It is somewhat disappointing to note that the new Figure 4D is not much of an improvement because the execution of the experimental design was faulty. The troubling question that remain is why Figures 1C, 2C, 3B and 7D were not also replaced. Figure 1C depicts Western Immunoblotting of PP-2A subunits that are anemic. Also, in Figure 1C, it appears that similar bands are present in all the lanes. It is interesting to note that the experimental design that gave rise to the data of Western Immunoblotting of PP-2A subunits in Figure 5 was performed correctly. The experimental design for Figures 1C, 2C, 3B and 7D should have been done in the same manner.

With respect to Figure S4, it was also flagged by anonymous writers in PUBPEER. Figure S4 showed clearly that there was unscientific manipulation of a Western Immunoblotting result. In this case, a tract was deliberately inserted.

In conclusion, the Journal of Cell Science graciously allowed the authors of the above paper to make certain corrections and to substitute certain figures [3]. The Journal of Cell Science did not retract the above paper sua sponte because it agreed with the recommendation of an Anonymous Scientific Panel at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS that concluded that there was no evidence of Scientific Misconduct due to Data Fabrication or Data Falsification [1,2]. The raw Scientific Data was apparently presented by the authors to the Anonymous Scientific Panel at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS and the latter was satisfied that the raw Scientific Data was legitimate and real. It is somewhat troubling that assembled Scientific Panel at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS chose to remain anonymous, especially considering the fact that the Respondents are being exonerated from any charges of misconduct with respect to the above paper. Presumably, the Scientific Panel at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS consists of recognized experts in the field and are senior members at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS so that they could not be target of retaliation in the event that they had ruled that there was occurrence of Scientific Misconduct. Because the appointed Scientific Panel at Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS consisted of

anonymous members, there will be suspicions of whitewashing. Indeed, there is a report from a group of anonymous writers [4] who are also Scientific Researchers that challenged the findings of the Anonymous Scientific Panel assembled by Universite Pierre et Marie Curie and CNRS. Also, because one the Respondents is a Senior Member of the CNRS (General Scientific Director of the Biological Sciences Division), there has been insinuations that there has been a cover up with respect to the investigation of alleged Scientific Misconduct in this particular case. Perhaps what is more puzzling is that the sole Complainants appear to be anonymous writers in PUBPEER.

As discussed previously by the author of this Report [5], when dealing with the serious matter of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud, Anonymous Postings do not help to resolve the controversies because the Respondents are being deprived of Due Process. If one is accused of wrong doing, one must be able to confront the accusers openly to defend one-self and there must be an impartial authority to investigate and issue adjudication. The same applies to the impartial authority. It cannot consist of Anonymous Individuals because questions of conflict of interest that may exist cannot be fully answered. It is the belief of the author of this report that the best solution to the problem is to have an Independent Commission or Body to investigate allegations of Scientific Misconduct and Scientific Fraud (ICISM), and an Independent Tribunal to Rule on Scientific Ethics Violations (ITRSEV [5]).

References

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